

Extraction of Fe^{III}, Sb^{III} and Cd^{II} from hydrochloric acid solution with organic extractant in methylisobutyl ketone

Yıldız Kalebaşı Aktaş* and Hilmi İbar

Trakya University, Department of Chemistry, 22030 Edirne, Turkey

E-mail : yilaktas@yahoo.com Fax : 90-284-2137053

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The extraction of Fe^{III}, Sb^{III} and Cd^{II} from hydrochloric acid solutions by neutral organophosphorus compounds (TBP[#], TOPO[#] and HDEHP[#]) and high molecular weight amine (TOA[#], R₃N) in MIBK[#] was investigated. It was found that the extraction efficiency for Fe^{III} is in the order : TOA = TBP > HDEHP > TOPO at low aqueous acidity and HDEHP = TOPO > TOA > TBP at higher acidity, for Sb^{III} is in the order : TOA > TOPO > HDEHP > TBP at low aqueous acidity and HDEHP > TOPO > TBP > TOA at higher acidity, and for Cd^{II} is in the order : TOPO = TOA > TBP > HDEHP at low aqueous acidity and TOA > TOPO > TBP > HDEHP at higher acidity. Batch method was used for the extraction of metals. The method was applied to the analysis of metals in waste water. In addition, the back-extraction for Fe, Sb and Cd were also studied. The interfering effects of Na, K, Mg, Ca, Co and Pb were investigated. Blank values were used and recoveries were 93.4, 91.0 and 96.5% for Fe, Sb and Cd, respectively, at 95% confidence level.

In the last several decades determination of elements by Flame Atomic Absorption as analytical technique in extraction systems have been described¹. We have presented a selective extraction system that will ensure complete and selective extraction of Fe, Sb and Cd in short time applicable to a large number of samples. It is well known that extraction of an ion from an aqueous solution is only possible if the charge is neutralized by chelation or by ion-association. A further requirements to aid the extraction is that at least one of the ions involved contains large hydrophobic groups. Bearing this in the mind, we thought that organophosphorous compounds like TBP, TOPO, HDEHP and TOA could be suitable for those purposes. TBP is one of the most widely used extractant, and found application for analytical purposes as well as for industrial applications. Extraction with TBP may proceed by various mechanisms². TOPO has also been used to extract several metals. HDEHP has found wide application for selective extraction and separation of a number of elements. It is also used in the extraction chromatography for impregnating stationary support phase³. TOA is a high molecular weight amine and is used for extraction of elements that yield anionic complexes, therefore in many cases chemical and electrostatical interactions are important⁴.

Among the variables that affect the extraction of metals

are pH, concentration of metals, complexing reagents, electrolyte and choice of diluent. The physical properties of solvents, such as density, viscosity and surface tension are responsible for better extraction and fast phase separation. Dielectric constant, polarity and polarizability can also influence solvent interaction. Among the solvents oxygen containing organic solvents such as MIBK is one of the most widely used diluent⁵. Their physicochemical properties enhances extraction and extracted species are stable. Extractants structure i.e. stereochemistry of complexing reagents and diluent plays important role in the stability of complexes and extraction process of the metals⁶.

Results and discussion

The results of the extraction of Fe^{III}, Sb^{III} and Cd^{II} from hydrochloric acid solutions are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Extraction (%) of Fe^{III}, Sb^{III} and Cd^{II} with HCl

Metal ion	[HCl], M	TOPO	TBP	HDEHP	TOA
Fe ^{III}	4.0	98	100	99.7	100
	8.0	100	95.2	100.0	97.2
Sb ^{III}	4.0	85	0.0	68.7	93.4
	8.0	83.7	82	93.4	73
Cd ^{II}	4.0	100	59.4	13.8	100
	8.0	93.5	81.5	59	100

*TBP = Tributyl phosphate, TOPO = Trioctyl phosphine oxide, HDEHP = Di-2-ethylhexylphosphoric acid, TOA = Trioctylamine, MIBK = methylisobutyl ketone.

The range of extraction for Fe lies between 95–100% which shows that used reagents are excellent extractants for Fe. Extraction of Fe follows the order : HDEHP = TOPO > TOA > TBP at high HCl acidity (8 M) and TOA = TBP > HDEHP > TOPO at low HCl acidity (4 M). The extraction efficiency for Sb follows the order : HDEHP > TOPO > TBP > TOA at high HCl acidity (8 M) and TOA > TOPO > HDEHP > TBP at low acidity (4 M). High extraction efficiency is obtained by TOA from 8 M HCl solutions and by HDEHP at lower acidity (4 M). Variation in HCl acidity effects to a large extent extraction of Sb with TBP, decreasing its extraction to a zero at 4 M HCl acidity. For Cd the range of extraction lies between 13–100%, following the order : TOA = TOPO > TBP > HDEHP at low acidity and TOA > TOPO > TBP > HDEHP at high (8 M) HCl acidity. HDEHP system is not a suitable extractant for Cd, while TOA can be considered as excellent for Cd extractions. TOPO and TOA appeared to be the most suitable extractant for studied elements.

The extracted metals can be back extracted (stripped) partially or completely from organic to the aqueous phase. In our study 0.5 mol L⁻¹ HCl, 1 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ and 0.5 mol L⁻¹ H₂O₂–0.5 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ were used as stripping solutions (Tables 1) and shows the amount of the back extracted metal species into aqueous phase.

For the TOA-MIBK system Fe was not back extracted by 0.5 mol L⁻¹ HCl + H₂O₂ and by 1 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ eluent

solution, but completely returned to the aqueous phase by other eluents. Sb was poorly back extracted by used eluent, with the exception of H₂O₂ + HNO₃, 0.5 mol L⁻¹ eluent from 8 M HCl solution system (91%). Cd was back extracted from organic phase to aqueous phase by 4 and 8 M HCl solutions.

Back extraction results for TBP-MIBK system only Fe was completely back extracted (100%) in all cases. Cd and Sb was not extracted at all and it seems that both metals are very strongly bonded to the TBP therefore used eluents are not effective in this case.

Back extraction results for HDEHP-MIBK system are not very effective (Table 3). Only Fe is completely stripped from low HCl solution, in others situations metals are not or partially back extracted into aqueous phase.

Determination of Fe, Sb and Cd in wastewater :

From the studied systems, TOPO-MIBK extraction system was applied for the determination of iron, antimony and cadmium in waste water samples. Wastewater samples were obtained from a factory near Edirne. An aliquot (300–500 ml) of the water sample was filtered to remove suspended materials, adjusted to the appropriate acidity with HCl, and then subjected to the used procedure. The analytical results are shown in Table 4. The method is useful for the analysis of water samples containing Fe^{III}, Sb^{III} and Cd^{II} in the environment.

Table 2. Effect of eluents on the back extraction of metal ions

Organic phase	Eluent	Back extraction (%) ^a		
		Fe ^{III}	Sb ^{III}	Cd ^{II}
TOPO-MIBK (4 M HCl)	HCl, 0.5 mol L ⁻¹	22.0 ± 3	44.2 ± 2	–
	HNO ₃ , 1 mol L ⁻¹	100 ± 2	–	89.9 ± 3
	H ₂ O ₂ + HNO ₃ , 0.5 mol L ⁻¹	100 ± 2	100 ± 1	100 ± 2
TOPO-MIBK (8 M HCl)	HCl, 0.5 mol L ⁻¹	77.0 ± 4	44.2 ± 7	22.2 ± 4
	HNO ₃ , 1 mol L ⁻¹	100 ± 3	7.7 ± 9	66.2 ± 2
	H ₂ O ₂ + HNO ₃ , 0.5 mol L ⁻¹	100 ± 1	100 ± 2	80.3 ± 3
TOA-MIBK (4 M HCl)	HCl, 0.5 mol L ⁻¹	–	23.1 ± 3	–
	HNO ₃ , 1 mol L ⁻¹	100 ± 1	37.9 ± 6	95.2 ± 3
	H ₂ O ₂ + HNO ₃ , 0.5 mol L ⁻¹	100 ± 2	72.0 ± 2	100 ± 2
TOA-MIBK (8 M HCl)	HCl, 0.5 mol L ⁻¹	–	–	–
	HNO ₃ , 1 mol L ⁻¹	100 ± 1	9.10 ± 1	74.6 ± 1
	H ₂ O ₂ + HNO ₃ , 0.5 mol L ⁻¹	100 ± 2	91.0 ± 2	96.5 ± 2
TBP-MIBK (4 M HCl)	HCl, 0.5 mol L ⁻¹	100 ± 3	–	8.3 ± 1
	HNO ₃ , 1 mol L ⁻¹	100 ± 4	–	–
	H ₂ O ₂ + HNO ₃ , 0.5 mol L ⁻¹	100 ± 1	–	–
TBP-MIBK (8 M HCl)	H ₂ O ₂ + HNO ₃ , 0.5 mol L ⁻¹	100 ± 2	–	–

^aAverage of three determinations.

Table 3. Effect of eluents on the back extraction of metal ions (HDEHP- MIBK)

Organic phase	Eluent	Back extraction (%) ^a		
		Fe ^{III}	Sb ^{III}	Cd ^{II}
HDEHP-MIBK (4 M HCl)	HCl, 0.5 mol L ⁻¹	100 ± 1	–	–
	HNO ₃ , 1 mol L ⁻¹	100 ± 3	18.9 ± 8	–
	H ₂ O ₂ + HNO ₃ , 0.5 mol L ⁻¹	93.4 ± 7	72.2 ± 6	–
HDEHP-MIBK (8 M HCl)	HCl, 0.5 mol L ⁻¹	81 ± 9	61.0 ± 4	23.2 ± 1
	HNO ₃ , 1 mol L ⁻¹	–	16.3 ± 9	–
	H ₂ O ₂ + HNO ₃ , 0.5 mol L ⁻¹	–	69.0 ± 4	–

^aAverage of three determinations with 95% confidence level.

Table 4. Determination of Fe, Sb and Cd in waste water and ground water sample using MIBK + TOPO system

Element	Waste water (mg L ⁻¹)	Ground water (mg L ⁻¹)	Added (mg L ⁻¹)	Waste water ^a Found (mg L ⁻¹)	Ground water ^a Found (mg L ⁻¹)
Fe	0.499 ± 1.2 × 10 ⁻²	0.013 ± 2.3 × 10 ⁻³	2.00	2.46 ± 1.1 × 10 ⁻²	2.011 ± 4.5 × 10 ⁻²
Sb	0.044 ± 3.1 × 10 ⁻³	0.011 ± 3.1 × 10 ⁻³	2.00	2.042 ± 4.1 × 10 ⁻³	2.009 ± 5.8 × 10 ⁻³
Cd	0.010 ± 2.2 × 10 ⁻³	0.004 ± 1.9 × 10 ⁻³	2.00	2.012 ± 2.5 × 10 ⁻²	2.003 ± 6.2 × 10 ⁻²

^aAverage of three determinations with 95% confidence level.

Effect of the diverse ions :

A sample solution of 1000 ml containing 10 mg Fe, 40 mg Sb and 5 mg Cd and metal ions (Na, K, Mg, Ca, Pb and Co (50 mg L⁻¹ each) were prepared. The extraction of Fe, Cd and Sb was carried out according to the procedure described above. It was observed that metal ions didn't interfere in the extraction of Fe, Sb and Cd.

Conclusion :

A simple, rapid and sensitive method combining liquid-liquid extraction and flame atomic absorption spectrometry were studied for the extraction of Fe^{III}, Sb^{III} and Cd^{II} from hydrochloric acid solutions by TBP, TOPO, HDEHP and TOA in methyl isobutyl ketone. The method was successfully applied for the determination of micro amounts of Fe^{III} and Sb^{III} and Cd^{II} from various aqueous HCl acid solutions. The proposed method exhibit good chemical stability, good analytical reliability and fast rate of equilibrium. Both, the extraction of the metals from the aqueous phase into organic phase and stripping of the metal ions from organic phase are fairly rapid. The interfering effects of several metal ions were studied and it was found that they do not interfere in the extraction of Fe^{III}, Sb^{III} and Cd^{II} from hydrochloric acid solution.

Experimental

Reagents :

TBP (Aldrich), TOPO and HDEHP (Alpha Aesar) and TOA (Merck) were used without further purification. Stock solutions of organic extractant were prepared by dissolving

7 ml of each reagent into 133 ml of MIBK.

Mixed standard solutions of, Fe (10 mg L⁻¹, Sb (40 mg L⁻¹) and Cd (5 mg L⁻¹) were prepared by appropriate dilution of 1000 mg L⁻¹ flame atomic absorption spectrophotometer (FAAS) standard stock solutions. In addition, stock solutions were diluted to appropriate concentration of HCl. Double-distilled water was used throughout. Other all chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Apparatus :

A UNICAM 929 model flame atomic absorption spectrophotometer (FAAS) was used with a UNICAM hollow cathode lamp and conventional 100 mm long burner head for air acetylene flame. The instrumental condition for each element was taken from the instrumental manual. The instrumental parameters were : sensitivity 0.060 mg L⁻¹; 0.370 mg L⁻¹; 0.032 mg L⁻¹; wave length 248.3; 217.6; 228.8 nm's respectively for Fe, Sb and Cd.

Extraction and analytical procedures :

Chloride complexes of Fe, Sb and Cd have been investigated with respect to their extractability by solutions of neutral organophosphoric extractant TBP, TOPO, HDEHP and TOA (5 percent each) as an amine extractant equal volumes (15 ml each of the aqueous and organic phases) were placed in 50 ml separatory funnel and shaken for 2 min after which content was allowed to stand for 1 h. The aqueous phase was separated from the organic phase and the metals extracted into organic phase were measured on the basis of the residual elements in the aqueous phase by FAAS.

Organic phase with the contents of extracted metals were back extracted into aqueous solution containing 0.5 mol L⁻¹ HCl, 1 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ and 0.5 mol L⁻¹ H₂O₂ + 0.5 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃. To the separatory funnel containing organic phase 15 ml of 0.5 mol L⁻¹ HCl, 1 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ and 0.5 mol L⁻¹ H₂O₂ + 0.5 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ were added and shaken for 2 min. After 1 h, aqueous solution was separated and metals extracted were determined.

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